

PROJECT FOR URBAN EXPERIENCE AND MOBILITY: DEVELOPING A PROJECT BASED ON EMOTIONAL REACTIONS FROM USERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates and suggests solutions that can be used to modify the waiting experience in urban mobility contexts for the better (evoking relaxation and pleasantness) through the use of sound stimuli. A workshop was held, after the observation of the habits of users, in order to design solutions for the qualification of the experience of bus passengers, which means, in this context, to be in a relaxed/pleasant emotional state, as well as to identify stimuli that could generate emotional responses that would be satisfactory for its users. The project envisages the development of bus stop prototypes with the incorporation of the solutions identified and designed during the study.

Keywords: design process, emotional design, experience, urban mobility.

INTRODUCTION

The design activity is strongly associated with the act of conceiving projects. Projects, in turn, are epistemologically related to the concept of being able to look forward, to anticipate the resolution of a problem. It can be represented by a game with changing and adaptable rules, depending on the circumstances and actors involved in it. Design can be understood as a game of prescriptive figuration, and it is temporally antecedent to the existence of the object in the world. If the design simply describes an existing state of affairs, it could not be termed as "design", because it would lack its nature of launching ahead time (SILVA, 2011).

For Dorst (2003), the design activity is characterized by determined, underdetermined, and undetermined

stages. The determined stages are highly conditioned by factors often external to the designer, such as legal requirements or even technological limitations. The underdetermined stages are characterized by interpretations of aspects that are peculiar to the design and the decision making process from a range of possibilities. Finally the undetermined stages are characterized by a high degree of freedom, closely linked to experience, style, and skill of the designer.

The existence of more or less determined stages caused the research in design to be guided by two paradigms that seek to explain the design process: a process of making satisfactory "rational" decisions and a process of making decisions whilst in action. The first had Herbert Simon as its main reference, and the second was represented by Donald Schön. In summary, we are working with two epistemological poles. The first follows a rational-positivist epistemology, while the second proposes a practical constructivist epistemology. The concept of reflection-in-action proposed by Schön is close to the concept of "intuition" as a process in which, to obtain certain knowledge (in this case, design knowledge), there is nothing that stands between the designer and what he or she is designing.

It is important to understand what is the origin of design as a professional activity. Every man can be understood as a designer, in the sense that every human being has the ability to design responses that solve problems of everyday life. However, some humans would be more designers than others, since they have been trained to develop this kind of activity. Some authors consider that design as an activity centered on the act of designing had its birth in the Renaissance, with the invention of perspective and

the separation between the act of thinking what will be done from the act of doing.

In this paper, the authors assume that the designing activity, as we know it today, had its origins in the Industrial Revolution, when a mostly handcrafted production was replaced by industrialized manufacturing. But this activity has changed significantly in recent decades. If at the end of the 19th century and first half of the 20th century the activity was closely linked to the designing of industrial artifacts, but the design activity has expanded. Nowadays, even talking about Service Design, Strategic Design, and Emotional Design, the Design activity is still holding its essence. However, designers also design "something" that does not exist in time and attempts to satisfy a predetermined objective, e.g. an experience.

Artifacts created by designers have always been agents that represent meanings and evoke emotions in people. What brings strength to these designs is the fact that these intangible elements can be consciously designed, with the emerging field of Design & Emotion. Design for Experience and Emotional Design fall within this spectrum.

Emotional design is understood as the field related to the professionalization of designing with the purpose of evoking or avoiding certain emotions (DEMIR, DESMET and HEKKERT, 2009). The relationship between user experience and emotion is unquestionable, because experience is, according to Pullman and Gross (2004, p. 551), emotional and personal, being dependent on individual factors such as cultural background, previous experiences, humor, and personality traits. Forlizzi, Ford, and Hanington (2003), as well as Hekkert and McDonagh (2003), assume that experience is unique, composed of small events related to contexts, products, and people, and that experiences are not designable. Only the situations of interaction with the users can be designed, evoking the intended emotions. Hekkert (2006) states that the product experience is strongly associated with affective content that is elicited by the interaction between the user and the product, including the degree to which the senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meaning attributed to the

product (experience of meaning), and the feelings and emotions evoked (emotional experience).

According to McLellan (2000), Design for Experience "orchestrates" experiences that are functional, engaging, compelling, and memorable. It requires designing every detail of the content and context, in order to evoke responses that are potentially gratifying in emotional terms (Kurtgozu, 2003). It is beyond the simple constitution of a service or product, but a whole set of activities of designing the processes and systems that give support for the experience, as well as the earlier stages of its constitution, such as a full understanding of the user's context and the production context.

This paper addresses a specific context of applying some of these concepts: the design of an experience with an "urban mobility" theme. Urban mobility has been a focus of interest to many experts, such as traffic engineers, city planners, politicians. The interest of this project, however, refers to a specific aspect of this system, which are bus stops.

Bus stops commonly evoke negative experiences. The waiting, discomfort, and insecurity are aspects often associated with these spaces in Brazil. This paper therefore addresses a theme that involves the daily life of millions of urban public transportation users. The quality of these services is in general quite deficient: the time spent and unpleasantness due to long waits can be sensed at bus stops in most large Brazilian cities. Thus, this context brings the question: Is it possible to design for alternative experiences that improve the conditions of this waiting, as well as the user's perception of quality of the transportation service?

The assumption made is that an experience of pleasure and relaxation can qualify people's perceptions about the Brazilian public transport system. Several experiments could be designed by to these experiences. In the case of this research, we aimed at investigating and suggesting solutions that can be used in future experiments to modify the waiting experience for the better (evoking relaxation and pleasantness) through the use of sound stimuli.

The choice of sound stimulation is easily understood. It is common sense that most Brazilians would like to have sound/music player devices whilst waiting for public transport. Any simple observation of everyday life in the country can show how popular those devices are.

In this research, three methodological steps were developed: (a) an *in loco* observation of bus stops to identify the potential of working with sound as a stimulus for a better experience, (b) a pre-project workshop that was intended to launch project ideas, and finally (c) the development of a test that evaluated sounds with a great potential to evoke the intended emotions (pleasantness and relaxation).

It is important to highlight that this paper presents research results (not design projects related to urban mobility), suggesting different tracks to develop design experiments. It shows the “reflection in action” (the process of making decisions whilst in action) which is Donald Schön’s way of understanding the design activity. It shows how design solutions can be sought whilst in the process of designing (SCHÖN,1993).

METHODS

IN LOCO OBSERVATION: WHAT ARE PEOPLE DOING OUT OF THE LAB?

Aiming at understanding which kind of stimuli/artifact people use to qualify the waiting experience in everyday situations, an *in loco* observation was developed, with the help of a group of undergraduate design students (Unisinos Design School). It is important to highlight that, by “qualify” we mean to keep a relaxed/pleasant emotional state, even being in a potentially unsafe, noisy, annoying situation.

The purpose of this first look at the phenomena was intended to feed the design process with inputs from real-world situations. To this end, the students were asked to observe and report people’s behaviors both in a park and in bus stops in the surroundings of the biggest park in town, registering the data both in a diary and in pictures, to understand what people do to be in a relaxed/pleasant emotional state. This setting was chosen due to its potential to make contrasts

clear: at one side a potentially stressful situation (bus stop) and, at the other side, a well-known relaxing environment (park). It is worth mention that the bus stops are known as stressful spots in the Brazilian city where the project was developed, since the crime rates and the crowded and noisy environment tend to make the experience poor to people.

The key-questions to guide the observations (observation guide) were:

- What people do during waiting times?
- Which kind of experience can you identify in the bus stop? Why? What seems to be pleasant / unpleasant, according to people, when asked about it?
- How people experience the waiting time? Which kind of emotion they report, when you ask about it?
- Which artifacts are used during the waiting time?

The observation was carried out during a Wednesday, a normal working day, in working hours. One of this paper’s authors was present in the spot the whole time, offering supervision to those who wanted to raise questions about any topic of the observation guide at any point during the observation.

The researcher asked the students to identify, as stated before in the text, which activities and artifacts seemed to be used, especially to evoke or maintain a relaxed/pleasant emotional state, suggesting where they would be positioned in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Circumplex Model of Affect (Desmet, 2008; adapted from Russell, 1980).

Even though the focus in this paper is not to discuss in depth the actual choice of sound to evoke a relaxed/pleasant emotional state, it is important to highlight that the arguments provided by people, and also observed by the students, include the potential to dissociate the person and the noisy environment; high control provided to people by artifacts that play music; The results have shown, in a brief description, several stimuli used by people to evoke or avoid the emotional states identified in the two axes seen on Figure 1, which are pleasantness/unpleasantness and calm/activated. It is important to highlight that all observations were also discussed with people that were in the actual setting, which means that the

the empowerment of personal taste, since it is controlled by the user; the fact that it can be used independent from others and the situation; and its potential to keep people's minds off their actual problems and/or avoiding focusing on the surrounding physical environment (dirtiness and dangers, e.g.).

WORKSHOP: HOW CAN WE USE THE INFORMATION ABOUT "WHAT ARE PEOPLE DOING OUT OF THE LAB?" TO DESIGN AN EXPERIENCE?

Based on the observation results as a starting point, a workshop was carried out with graduate design students and this paper's authors, aiming at developing design projects, focusing on qualifying the waiting experience. It happened in two separate days,

Figure 2: Activities and hypothesized organization regarding pleasantness and activation.

students, after looking for "signs of relaxation and pleasantness", also spoke to people to better understand them and their context.

Results pointed at the use of sound as a stimulus to be considered in our project, as expected, and as it can be noticed in Figure 2:

organized as follows:

Day 1

- The first stage of the workshop, defined as "sensibilization", exposed the students to the concepts of Design for Experience, Design for Emotions and the observation results.

- The “instructions” represented the second stage of the workshop, and included both the workshop’s structure and the general aim of the project (to qualify the waiting experience).
- Brief presentation: The brief was presented to the workshop participants as follows: “Some sound stimuli have the potential to evoke certain emotional responses on people. The aim of the workshop will be to work on design ideas brought by an in loco observation, aiming at evoking pleasantness and relaxation on public transport users. Such emotions, however, should be caused by material artifacts. Thus, a secondary objective of the workshop is the idealization of these artifacts. Such artifacts can be used in future research trials.
- After the briefing, the participants were split into four groups and began the work under the guidance of three teachers who conduct the process.

Day 2

- Each group discussed conceptually what kind of artifact would be developed. By throwing out words, the group underwent processes of filtering and/or building semantic maps. The results of this process were presented in concepts represented graphically. Some processes and results that the groups reached are presented as follows.

The group defined as "bubble", based on the relationship between "calm" and "active", associated respectively with the word "calm" the concepts of individual, well-being, contemplation, distraction, safety, rhythm, silence, and observation. As for the word "active", the words break from routine, colors, history, challenge, change, anxiety, attention, curiosity, clock, and noise were associated. They designed an artifact that, playing with equipment that provides tissue to dry hands in bathrooms, would provide bubble wrap (used to package products) for people to pop. The idea tries to cause a surprise factor and play with people's imagination who spend their time "popping" air bubbles (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Bubble wrap holder. In the picture, written in Portuguese, are the words: "Dry hands with only 2 sheets".

Even though the idea might sound inadequate to evoke pleasantness and relaxation, popping bubble wrap is a very popular Brazilian activity. It is usually connected with the idea of a childish and fun activity.

The second group went through a structured process in another way. They created two concept maps related to the words "unpleasant" and "pleasant". These maps were represented by moodboards as seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Maps and moodboards. On the top map appear the following words associated with Unpleasant: upset, individualism, stress, cold, inconvenient, irritable, poor operation, hyperstimulation, excess, uninteresting, abandonment disharmony, unsynchronized. On the bottom map are the following words associated with Pleasant: beauty, color, nature, harmony, interest, company, sympathy, heat, fascination, leisure, entertainment, liberty, choices, good operation, organization.

This stage led the group to imagine an environment based on ideas of fun, competition, and customization, as a way of appropriating the bus stop

to make them more expressive and with their own identity. This group also proposed to create elements that would stimulate the imagination of natural environments outside the urban context of large cities. The development of the project used the concept of the game "genius". The group proposed a space for games and touch panels where users could freely create graffiti and customize the bus stop (Figure 5).

Figure 5: A space for games, entertainment, with its own identity.

The researchers evaluated the concept bus stop as another solution connected to a funny base. Although it can be understood as a design very close to the first one in terms of its aims (fun activities), it also reflects the game culture that some of these students were part of.

The third group designed a device intended to relieve irritation. It was ment to be used as an instrument that would be placed at the disposal of users. Instead of worrying about evoking calm and relaxation, this group envisioned a mechanism to express angryness, through sound amplification. To make this proposal tangible, the group used a different environment from a bus stop. They used a snack shop known for its slowness in serving simple daily meals. The device has been called "the yell" (Figure 6).

Figure 6: the yell.

Even being evaluated as an interesting mechanism to express angryness, it was judged by the researchers as poorly connected to the main objective of the project, which was to evoke pleasantness and relaxation. It seemed more like a placebo solution to express bad emotions that should be avoided by the project.

Once the concepts generated during the workshop were envisioned, an attempt was made to explore more the emotional dichotomy of the pleasant and unpleasant dimensions. The decision was made at that point to develop a prototype of a chair/seat that could use sound elements as a means of generating positive or negative emotional reactions in the user. This decision was based on the recurrence of sound as a stimuli to evoke pleasantness and relaxation both at the first stage of the project (the *in loco* observation) and the workshop.

To develop the prototype, the researchers carried out a survey to test stimuli that have great potential to evoke pleasantness and relaxation. The survey is described in the following section, as well as its results.

“SOUND SURVEY”: HOW CAN WE CERTIFY THAT WE ARE USING THE RIGHT STIMULI TO DESIGN AN EXPERIENCE?

Whichever direction is defined in an experience-driven project, it is important to make sure that the stimuli used to design an experience have a great potential to make the intended change. Based on this idea, the stimuli chosen in the workshop to evoke a relaxed/pleasant emotional state among people during waiting periods were tested.

In order to avoid the effect of personal taste, or preferences, related to the sound stimuli, or even the interference of voice over the users' evaluations, the choice was to select a few sounds that were “pure sounds”, meaning non-musical, without mixing different stimuli, as linking voice and musical instruments. Ten sounds were chosen to be tested: Harley Davidson in use, sea waves, birds (alarm), water fountain, woods and animals, baby laugh, bells, fireworks, dog barking and rooster.

Forty-three graduate and undergraduate Brazilian students took part in this stage of the project. They were exposed, in groups, to different stimuli, one at a time, chosen from the workshop results. To each one of these stimuli, participants answered two questions, namely the pleasantness and the arousal dimensions of the Manikins (Bradley & Long, 1994) as measurement technique. The results were analyzed through an ANOVA, using the SPSS, point at the stimuli with the greatest potential to evoke relaxation/pleasantness.

Results showed that the sound of the water fountain was the best one to evoke responses of relaxation ($M=2,47$, $Std.Dev=0,27$), compared to all the other nine stimuli in test ($ps<0,05$). It was also the best one to evoke pleasantness ($M=6,74$, $Std.Dev=0,35$), compared to all the others ($ps<0,05$), apart from woods and animals and baby laugh, that had equivalent means ($ps>0,05$).

Curiously, the worst ones to evoke relaxation were the sounds of motorcycle and bells, followed by baby laugh, fireworks, dog barking and rooster crowing. The ones with the poorest potential to evoke pleasantness were motorcycle, bells, dog barking and rooster crowing.

Results showed an obvious yet interesting stimulus to be used in the "relaxing chair", which is the sound of a water fountain. Thus, the challenge of qualifying the waiting experience in urban mobility contexts in Brazil continues, since the following steps of our project is the actual design, and its respective test in real-world contexts.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

By observing the way in which people use their waiting time to inspire design, it was possible to develop actual ideas to qualify the waiting experience. To develop a meaningful experience design project, the authors have used stimuli that were already in the original context (bus stops/parks) and that seemed to be used to the same purposes of the project, meaning the qualification of an unwanted situation.

Starting from the idea generation (workshop), we made the choice of working with sounds. Again, sound stimuli is quite popular among public transport users and it seems related to disconnecting them from the noisy and stressful environment. The final stage of the study indicated, through the test of sound stimuli, that pleasantness and relaxation can be evoked among the users.

This paper was aimed at describing the process of investigating and suggesting solutions that could be used to modify the waiting experience in urban mobility contexts to evoke relaxation and pleasantness through the use of sound stimuli. The next stage of this study is to evaluate the reactions from public transport users to the stimuli identified. They will be, in a first stage, tested in an artificial environment, in which the chair/seat prototype will be placed within the university, and then used by whoever is in this environment. From the analysis of these results, a prototype of the bus stop should be developed, incorporating elements of sound, previously identified and tested. In a final stage, the users reactions will be evaluated in a natural context of use (bus stop).

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